

Violence against women: Definition, types and the role of men

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Abstract. Violence against women is still a social problem that needs to be solved in almost all societies because women have been more delicate, weak or more sensitive than men from past to present. In addition to business and social life, violence experienced especially in the marriage union, which is the basis of society, causes severe damage to family life. In this study, qualitative systematic review design with literature review variant were used to understand and to interpret the definition of violence against women, types and the role of men in violence against women. As a result, it can be said that violence, which is a social problem, cannot be solved only by legal regulations for women who are victims of violence, men who perpetrate violence should also be a part of this solution and it is important for women to have economic independence at every stage of their lives.

Keywords: Violence, woman, men, law, practice

Introduction

Violence against women remains a pervasive social issue that requires urgent resolution in nearly all societies. Historically, women have often been perceived as more delicate, vulnerable, or sensitive compared to men. This perception, combined with violence experienced in various spheres of life particularly within marriage, the foundational unit of society-inflicts significant harm on family life.

Violence against women is a violation of human rights and a form of discrimination against women. It can take many forms, including physical violence, sexual abuse, female genital mutilation or forced marriage. (Chapman, 1990). The phenomenon of violence is seen as the biggest problem that damages, harms and even disrupts the quality of life of individuals and societies, social peace, success and family unity, creates negative effects in every field, and is seen as a problem in all societies from past to present. When the act of violence is examined in detail, it is seen that individuals who are considered weak in terms of self-defense, women, children, the elderly and disabled individuals are subjected to violence.

The fight against violence against women started in 1987 with the “March against Battering” (T.C. Ministry of Family and Social Policies, 2015), which was the result of the women's movement against violence and the protests against violence as women were more frequently harmed by the violent incidents in which they were involved. Law No. 4320 on the Protection of the Family and Law No. 6284 on the Protection of the Family and Prevention of Violence against Women were expanded in line with the problems, deficiencies and needs experienced in practice. Although the laws have been revised, the incidents of violence against women are increasing in frequency every day and the consequences are more complex and severe.

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In this article it was aimed to define violence against women, the types of violence against women, the role of men in violence against women. Thus, following research questions were sought to answer based on literature on violence against women:

1. What is the definition of violence against women?
2. What are the types of violence against women?
3. What is the role of men in violence against women?

Methodology

Method and paradigm of research

This study is a qualitative descriptive analysis grounded in a literature review, a variation of the systematic review design. A literature review is typically defined as a systematic approach to collecting and synthesizing prior research (Günbayi, 2020; Baumeister & Leary, 1997; Cooper, 1998). The research paradigm guiding this study is interpretive, which seeks to empathize with individuals' experiences and uncover the deeper desires and meanings within the subjectivity of human life (Günbayi, 2018; Günbayi & Sorm, 2020).

Sampling

The research population comprises articles, books, and reports on violence against women published over the past 35 years. The study utilized criterion sampling, a type of purposive sampling technique, to select the research sample.

Data collection and analysis techniques

Document analysis was employed as the data collection technique. Data were gathered from articles, books, and reports related to violence against women, published within the last 35 years. A keyword search using terms such as "violence against women," "types of violence against women," and "the role of men in violence against women" was conducted on Google Scholar to identify relevant literature.

Data analysis

Descriptive analysis, a qualitative data analysis method, was applied in this study. Descriptive analysis involves summarizing and interpreting the collected data according to pre-established or emerging themes (Gunbayi, 2023).

Findings

Based on literature review on violence against women, this section covers the definition, the types, the role of men in violence against women.

Definition of violence against women

It is difficult and complex to define violence because it is interpreted differently in different disciplines. Analyses of violence by different disciplines show that violence has a multidimensional and complex nature (Aktürk & Doğan, 2013). Violence has become a frequently encountered situation in both public and private life. According to the Turkish Language Association, violence is defined as: "The degree of a movement, a force, intensity, harshness. The use of brute force against those with opposing views.

Brute force. Excessiveness in emotion or behavior” (TDK, 2024). As can be understood from the definition, violence is a harsh, rude and unwanted situation by the other party.

When we look at the meanings of the word; the word violence has the meanings of “strictness”, “hardness”, “excessiveness”, “tightness” (TDK, 2024). When we examine the Greek Latin-English languages, we see that the word has the meanings of “violating, violating, disrupting” as well as “force” and “power” (Dursun, 2011). Violence against women is defined as “perhaps the most shameful and widespread violation of human rights” (Özkan, 2017).

From past to present, violence is a dangerous behavior that causes unrest, uneasiness and sometimes death (Zara & İnci, 2008). The aim of violence is to establish a hegemony in the physical or psychological field or to ensure the continuity of the existing hegemony. This hegemony is manifested and perpetuated through physical or psychological violence against women. The violence used by men in order to achieve the dominance they try to achieve over women is used as a means of establishing, proving and maintaining authority (Aktürk & Doğan, 2013).

The World Health Organization's 2002 “World Report on Violence and Health” defines violence as “the intentional use of physical force or coercion against oneself, another person or a group or community that is likely to cause, or has a high probability of causing, actual injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment or deprivation” (WHO, 2002).

Gender-based violence takes many forms: physical, sexual, emotional, and psychological. Examples include female genital mutilation, killing in the name of so-called ‘honor’, murder, forced and early marriage, and sex trafficking. Two of the most prevalent types of violence that women experience are intimate partner violence (IPV) and non-partner sexual violence (NPSV) (World Bank, 2022).

Types of violence against women

Violence against women, which is one of the forms of human rights violation and discrimination against women due to gender inequality, is inflicted on women because they are women. Violence against women is directed against women by men they know and men they do not know, especially men in their immediate environment (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015).

All women around the world, regardless of country, ethnicity, class, religion, economic and/or social status, face the risk of being subjected to gender-based violence (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015). The emergence of violence against women usually occurs at the beginning of family life (Hatunoğlu, Hatunoğlu, & Avcı, 2014). In patriarchal societies dominated by men, women are given responsibilities above their capacity, and when they cannot fulfill their responsibilities, they face violence (Şenol & Yıldız, 2013). Violence takes place not only on the street or in work life, but also within or outside the family. In addition, the perpetrator of violence against women is not always only the spouse, but it can also occur between relatives who share the same house (Ünlü, 2013).

The 2015 surveys conducted by the Ministry of Family and Social Policies show similar results, although there are some differences. In a study conducted in collaboration with Hacettepe University, 36% of women stated that they had been subjected to physical violence and 12% to sexual violence at some point in their lives, while 38% of women had been subjected to at least one of the two forms of violence, indicating that sexual violence is often combined with physical violence. Increasing education level decreases the percentage of exposure to physical or sexual violence (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015).

Instead of considering violence against women as a simple crime, it should also be evaluated in terms of its impact on public resources. In addition to human resources, research shows that violence has huge economic costs, including direct costs to health, legal, police and other services, and undermines efforts to reduce girls' school enrolment and improve women's access to education. The World Health Organization discussed violence against women in detail at the 69th World Health Assembly meeting

and stated that women are affected by different forms of gender-based violence at different stages of their lives and that women are subjected to violence through domestic violence, sexual violence, human trafficking, femicide and sexual harassment (WHO, 2016).

When we look at violence against women, we see that it is divided into various types. It is seen in many research and published reports that violence is subjected to discrimination. Violence is firstly considered as intense physical impact and pressure on the other party all over the world. Even if various types of violence are known, it is generally considered as physical violence in daily life. There are many reasons for violence in our country and in the world. Economic difficulties, psychological reasons, cultural roles, social relations, the aim of establishing superiority, etc. can be counted.

Domestic violence

The applicability of human rights machinery to the abuse of and violence against women was first seriously addressed internationally at the U.N. Mid-Decade Conference on Women held in Copenhagen in 1980. The conference found that "domestic violence was a complex problem and constituted an intolerable offense to the dignity of human beings (Chapman, 1990). In order for violence to be considered as domestic violence, it is not necessary for the perpetrator and the victim to share the same residence; violence that occurs between couples who are living together even if they do not have an ongoing or previous family relationship (divorced spouses) or even if there is no formal union (marriage) is meant.

Domestic violence is defined as aggressive behavior and threats against one's spouse, children and relatives (Öztürk, 2014). Domestic violence against women is generally seen to stem from the fact that women live economically and culturally dependent on men and are subjected to social discrimination. Research shows that domestic violence against women is most frequently directed against women by their husbands or intimate partners (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015).

Although there are times when men are also subjected to violence, children are also subjected to violence in most of the domestic violence incidents in which the leading role is played by women, but the ways in which men and women cope with violence differ (Kuzu, 2013). Apart from the roles previously assigned to women by Turkish society, women's desire to change their place in society or to acquire new roles is effective in the formation and development of self-confidence, and unfortunately, attempts to prevent behaviors that patriarchal society cannot adopt unfortunately end with violence (Gülpınar & Kandemirci, 2013). Some problems occur in the self-identity of women who are subjected to violence, and it affects women deeply mentally and physically. Women's being subjected to violence destroys their self-confidence and leads to the fear that they may face violence again at every moment of their lives.

Similarly in most societies, men's violent behaviors aimed at establishing superiority over their wives can be explained by their desire to establish dominant authority in the family. Considering that men are socially supported in patriarchal societies such as our country, it is possible to come across violent behaviors to seize and maintain authority quite commonly. The most painful fact about domestic violence against women is that it is repeated over and over again, and that the violence is not perpetrated by a stranger, but by a spouse, relative or friend. Most of the time, women are subjected to violence by their husbands or intimate partners whom they have married out of love and trust and with whom they have children. Domestic violence against women, which is a widespread problem, is also related to individual and social aspects. Regardless of the cause, many people are affected by domestic violence. Both the perpetrator, the victim and the witnesses of this violence are negatively affected separately (Kandemirci & Kağnıcı, 2014).

Women's lack of self-confidence, lack of economic freedom and having a traditional perspective can be considered among the general characteristics of women who are subjected to domestic violence. Physical, emotional, sexual and economic violence may vary according to geographical or spatial

location, as well as the age, education, employment status, marital status and economic level of the victims.

Physical violence

All aggressive behaviors based on the use of physical force and aimed at physically harming living beings are considered as physical violence (Atman, 2003). It is defined as the most common type of violence against women (Yetim & Şahin, 2008) and the type of violence that women are most exposed to, which consists of actions that start with minor injuries and continue to increase until the end of murder (Şener, 2011). The fact that men are physically stronger and more durable than women leads to the emergence of violence in the resolution of disputes (Şenol & Yıldız, 2013). The power and physical actions applied with the use of physical muscle power can be characterized as the state of being physically attacked. These can be graded as follows:

- Moderate physical violence:
 - Slapping or throwing something
 - Pushing, shoving, or pulling hair
- Severe physical violence:
 - Hitting with a fist or an object
 - Kicking, dragging or beating
 - Squeezing the throat or burning apart of the body
 - Threatening or using tools such as knives and guns

In Turkey 19% of married women have been subjected to moderate physical violence and 16% to severe physical violence at some point in their lives. As the level of damage caused by violent behavior increases, its prevalence decreases (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015).

Violence is the actions and behaviors that men, who have a stronger structure in terms of body muscle structure compared to women, exhibit in order to make women accept their demands, to prevent the behaviors they do not want, to wear the woman down, and to harm the woman's body. Such behaviors can sometimes be seen even by the woman's own family as behaviors that her husband can do.

Psychological violence

Although this type of violence does not physically harm women, it causes great psychological damage. It is the type of violence that causes the most damage to women's self-realization and development in society (İlkkaracan & Gülçür 1996). Emotional violence/abuse against women by their husband(s) or intimate partner(s) (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı, 2015):

- Insult or swearing,
- Humiliation or humiliation in front of others,
- Intimidation or threats,
- Threatening to harm women or those around them.

Making accusations that a woman cannot do a job, that she cannot succeed, disregarding her personality and ideas, insulting her, shouting at her, ignoring her, calling her unpleasant nicknames, constantly criticizing her actions and thoughts in order to humiliate her in society, to keep her away from work life, to reduce her dignity, to harm her personality by belittling her, making demands in the form of orders to do what they want, keeping their behaviors and actions under constant control like an employer or owner, preventing women from opportunities that come their way in order to keep them away from business life or humiliate them, and keeping them unaware (Uluocak, et al, 2014).

The General Directorate on the Status of Women recognizes emotional violence as “any act of systematic psychological pressure, emotional exploitation and humiliation against someone, and any action taken to isolate them from society in order to control or punish them.”(KSGM, 2009).

Psychological violence: “Shouting, insulting, swearing, threatening, intimidating, humiliating, ridiculing, not allowing her to make decisions, comparing her with other women and men, not allowing her to improve herself, not allowing her to meet with her family, friends, neighbors, not allowing her to go out of the house, checking her whereabouts at any time, belittling her beliefs - her origin - her job - her salary, constantly interrupting her in front of others, etc.” are behaviors of psychological violence against women. (KSGM, 2009).

Since male hegemony is dominant in *Turkey*, women are often seen as weak and to be managed in the family or in business life. Due to culture, traditions or regional customs, even if they do not want to accept it, men may see women as a weak being, a person to be dominated and managed. Even if there are differences between regions, in general, in our country, which still has a social structure dominated by male domination, if the woman does not fulfill the wishes of the man, the man inflicts various types of violence on her.

The psychological tendencies he will exhibit in order to put pressure, subjugate, make her do what he wants, make her dependent on him, isolate her, and prevent her progress and development lead to psychological violence. Psychological violence is mostly perpetrated by men who are insecure, rude, have personality disorders, have been raised in the wrong family environment and have been subjected to violence in their childhood.

Sexual violence

Sexual violence is a form of violence that occurs all over the world. Although little research has been done on the problem in most countries, available data shows that in some countries, about one in four women are victims of intimate partner sexual violence and about one-third of adolescent girls are victims of sexual violence. Sexual violence has a profound impact on physical and mental health. In addition to causing physical injury, it is associated with a range of risks of sexual and reproductive health problems, with both short and long-term consequences. Its impact on mental health can be as serious as its physical impact and equally long-lasting. Deaths following sexual violence can occur as a result of suicide, HIV infection or homicide. Sometimes violence changes direction with “honor killings” after sexual violence. Sexual violence can also profoundly affect the social well-being of victims; individuals may be stigmatized and ostracized by their families and others (WHO, 2002).

The World Health Organization defines sexual violence as “behaviors such as forcing sexual intercourse, engaging in unwanted sexual behaviors, harassment, making criticisms and words emphasizing sexuality, and making unwanted sexual conversations” (WHO, 2010). Accordingly, pressure and coercion can be physical as well as psychological. In the phenomenon of sexual violence against women, it continues to exist as a type of violence in societies where sexuality is seen as a taboo and concepts such as honor and honor, especially for women, are defined through women's sexuality.

Sexual violence, mostly against women, is a type of violence related to sexual activity. Acts and practices such as forcing a person to have sexual intercourse against their will, causing them to contract sexually transmitted infectious diseases, forcing them against their will during sexual intercourse, hurting them, raping them, hurting them, damaging their body, forcing them to have sex with other people, having intercourse at times against the woman's will, causing them to become pregnant by refusing contraceptives despite the woman's wishes, damaging their genitals, accusing them of being a prostitute, etc., which is not welcomed in the society, oppressing them due to the sense of honor and tradition of the region where they live, and resorting to physical violence. Actions and practices such as accusing the woman of being a prostitute, etc., putting pressure on her due to her region's understanding of honor and tradition, and resorting to physical violence can be grouped under this heading (Akkaş, 2016).

Sexual violence practiced under the habits, culture or traditions of the region in which the women live is usually accompanied by physical violence. Traditional roles of femininity and masculinity can form the basis of this violence. Sexual violence, which is seen as an intimate area or taboo that is not wanted

to be heard, preferred to remain hidden and considered shameful, is also a very difficult phenomenon to detect. It would not be wrong to say that sexual violence is the type of violence that women have difficulty in complaining, explaining and hesitating (Adak, 2000). Sexual violence against women perpetrated by husband(s) or intimate partner(s) (T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Politikalar Bakanlığı):

- Forced sexual intercourse,
- A woman has sexual intercourse out of fear, even though she does not want to,
- Being forced to perform sexually degrading or humiliating acts,

can be briefly explained as “sexual violence”. In closed societies, sexual violence against women remains hidden, and women who do not want their names to be associated with this type of violence cannot file a complaint, and there are problems in conducting clear research on how often it occurs.

Economic violence

Economic violence against women encompasses acts of preventing women from working or forcing them to work without their knowledge or control. The reasons and types of women's exposure to economic violence may vary (Uluocak, et al, 2014);

- Controlling the woman's money, not making her spend it, taking her money from her,
- Giving insufficient money for the will of the house,
- Confiscating your credit card,
- Forced labor,
- Taking property rights by force,
- Preventing, obstructing, canceling education.

Economic violence includes actions such as taking women's money, not employing them, forcing them to work, preventing them from spending money, preventing them from education, rendering them unable to work, preventing them from buying movable or immovable property or converting existing ones into their own name, spending/investing or changing family savings in different places without the woman's knowledge or consent.(KSGM, 2009). The Ministry of Family and Social Policies also cites similar reasons for economic violence against women: “Economic violence/abuse against women by husband(s) or intimate partner(s) (T.C. Ministry of Family and Social Policies):

- Preventing a woman from working or causing her to quit her job,
- Not giving money for household expenses,
- Taking away a woman's income” as economic violence.

It is known that women, who constitute about half of the population in the world and in our country, do not have the opportunity to be represented at the same rate in their participation in economic activities. According to 2022 data, the labor force participation rate of women in the world is 47.4%, lagging behind that of men (72.3%) (ILO, 2023). Similarly, in Turkey, the labor force participation rate of women is 36.6%, lower than that of men (71.9%) (TÜİK, 2022).

Since a woman deprived of economic freedom will be dependent on her man/husband, she will be silent about other forms of violence perpetrated by him, and he will be able to further consolidate his dominance over her. In order to prevent all forms of violence against women, it is necessary to ensure that women are well educated, taught their rights and have enough income to survive economically on their own. A woman who is freed from economic dependence will feel stronger, will not be dependent on the man/husband and submit to his/her wishes, and when she is subjected to violence, she will be able to make the necessary complaints to get rid of this violence or to separate the union if the violence still continues.

Social Violence

Although violence against women has been seen as a women's problem for years, this act is a global human problem that transcends cultural, geographical, religious, social and economic boundaries (Körükçü, Kayır & Kukulu, 2012). The way violence is practiced, its frequency and consequences may vary from society to society according to social cultures.

Violence against women is not an individual problem, but rather a multidimensional problem that needs to be investigated in every aspect from the family to the society. It may stem from gender inequality or the predetermined role of women in gender perception. The Turkish Language Association defines the word gender with a biologically based approach as “the characteristic of creation that gives the individual a separate role in reproduction and at the same time distinguishes between male and female, sexuality, sex” (TDK, 2024). Biological gender, which defines the physical differences between individuals, should be distinguished from social gender.

Restriction or prevention of rights such as the right to life, health and nutrition, education, self-development, participation in social and economic life, which are stated as fundamental human rights and freedoms, is an important social problem. In our country, as in many parts of the world, gender-based violence occurs in order to keep women under their control, to maintain their superiority and to exert pressure to force them to do what they want under the influence of the male-dominated social structure and may be considered reasonable by some societies. Some social conditions and assumptions render women powerless in the face of men and position men as strong and powerful. In societies where men are seen as superior to women, violence against women can be used to ensure and maintain the power of men over women (Acar, 2013).

Violence is directed against everyone, but it especially targets women and girls as they are more vulnerable and weaker. It can take place in physical, sexual, psychological, economic and other forms. Anyone can commit violence, but the perpetrator needs to be stronger. In general, violence in society can become more widespread when the authorities do not fully implement the laws or ignore them (Uluocak, et al, 2014).

In order to ensure that women do not fall behind in social life and assume a more active role, they should be provided with the necessary facilities for their training and even encouraged with positive discrimination. When literacy rates are analyzed in general, illiteracy rates are higher among women than men, and this rate remains relatively high in rural areas and among older women (TUİK, 2024). Women who are illiterate enough to express themselves will continue to be under the influence of men and will be one of the biggest obstacles to their active participation in social and community life.

Violence against women continues to be an ongoing problem in our country as in many other countries. It is also one of the most important social problems in Turkey. When violence against women is examined, it is an extremely common problem in all cultures, regardless of the places where societies live, geographical borders, the level of development of the country and the level of education

Role of men in violence against women

The United Nations has predicted that the inclusion of men in the issue will lead to a significant improvement in achieving gender equality. Studies show that men are a major part of the solution in preventing violence against women and focus on giving them roles and responsibilities. There are many innovative studies on gender equality and violence against women, especially for men (Körükçü, Kayır & Kukulu, 2012).

The most well-known of these efforts and the largest men's movement in the world is the “White Ribbon” campaign, which has taken place in more than 60 countries. This campaign started in 1991 with the aim of bringing a new perspective to men and raised awareness about preventing gender inequality, ending violence against women and building healthy relationships in society. The campaign aimed to

identify the reasons why men resort to violence and what needs to be done together with the perpetrators to prevent violence. Over the past years, the role of men in preventing violence against women has increased considerably and joint efforts have been made with men to make them an important factor in ending violence. The most prominent of these is the white ribbon campaign around the world. In this way, there has been an increase in the arguments used to prevent violence. Since men are at the top of the power and decision-making units of many committees around the world, their role and power in economic, political and social fields are seen as important for the elimination of violence (National Community of Practice, 2015).

It is assumed that low self-confidence, the culture, traditions and habits of the family and environment in which they were raised are effective in men who resort to violence. As seen in some regions of our country, violence is more common in family structures where men are dominant in society (Delice, 2013). This situation affects the process of transferring gender roles from generation to generation in the definition of gender. In determining the position of women in society, changing the perception of men about violence against women is of great importance in ensuring gender equality. Studies have shown that men in Turkey adopt traditional roles more than women (KSGM, 2009).

Society's perspective on women should be changed and it should be recognized that they have an important place in the social structure. Violence against women must be eliminated. In order to prevent this violence, women's perspective on their own status and rights should be changed rather than only educating men, informing the society or imposing sanctions on men. The active participation of women in social life and the successful overcoming of the problems they face in this process require the participation and support of men (KSGM, 2009). With a holistic approach, the problem can be solved more easily with the participation of both men and women.

Conclusion

As a result of the literature review and academic research on violence against women, it was concluded that violence against women is seen in all races, languages, religions or societies without discrimination. In interviews with women victims of violence, it was concluded that women's level of education, country of origin, whether they are married or single, whether they are employed or not, cannot be accepted as a single or collective reason for experiencing violence or staying away from violence.

As a result, women can be subjected to violence in our country and in any part of the world, and new laws, practices and protection measures are on the agenda in order to prevent this. The planned new legal changes and measures should be evaluated within the framework of the unique characteristics of societies. It is clear that the establishment of a separate unit, institution or ministry specialized in the protection of women in our country, determining new policies in line with the expectations of women who are subjected to violence, and establishing different assistance centers (such as psychological, economic, health, educational support) will make important contributions to the solution of the problem. However, in view of the fact that this problem is not a problem specific to our country, in order to prevent violence, it is seen as the most important solution tool to increase the level of social awareness by placing the problem in the curricula of courses starting from primary education, which is the first level of education.

Recommendations

Under this heading, suggestions that women victims of violence can do in the face of violence and that are likely to be implemented to prevent violence at the individual level and to eliminate the problems encountered in the security units and that are thought to contribute to the prevention of violence are included.

Recommendations on victims' behavior against violence

Violence is a crime against humanity that is unworthy of humanity and must be eliminated by all societies, regardless of who it comes from and who it is directed against. Regardless of whether the victim is a woman or a child, or regardless of the motive of the perpetrator, violence should be recognized as a fundamental problem that must be prevented.

It is clear that the behavior and thoughts of women who are subjected to violence against this problem are the primary issue in eliminating the crime. Therefore, in order to eliminate violence against women, first of all, the idea that violence is a crime against society and humanity should be instilled in the individual within the family. For this reason, the social idea of inequality between men and women, which is the accumulation of centuries, should be eliminated by using belief systems within the family. It should not be forgotten that it is ultimately a woman who raises the man who perpetrates violence and the task of preventing violence is primarily based on the education to be provided by mothers. For this reason, all public institutions and organizations should act in cooperation and ensure the implementation of the laws to prevent the exclusion of girls from education, which is still a serious problem in our society.

Regardless of the source and cause of violence against women, it should be recognized that the understanding that violence against women is a misguided belief and the social understanding that women should accept it with resignation should be eliminated.

Within the education process, the equality of women and men and the fact that the family is the cornerstone of society and that spouses build this foundation together should be taught to young people in citizenship lessons and other courses. Case studies and literary works that will ensure this should be recommended as source books and made available for reading.

Recommendations for police departments

In order to overcome these problems, first of all, it would be appropriate for police centers, which are the place of application for victims of violence, to be handled by separate units in accordance with the importance of the situation, for example within the children's branch directorate.

It is necessary to expand the powers of the law enforcement units that carry out the investigation process with legal regulations to take different measures for the victims and the perpetrators of violence, taking into account the developing conditions and situations, provided that the fear and anxiety of women who have been subjected to violence in any period of their lives and who have complained to the relevant authorities do not end after the complaint.

One of the most important issues is to revise the existing practices by the relevant institutions and organizations in order to fulfill the demands of women victims of violence regarding shelter, asylum, etc. by law enforcement units and to provide services to women victims of violence in good environments and conditions even on a (24) hour basis. In particular, it is considered that the uncompromising application of sanctions to be imposed on the perpetrator of violence, especially compulsory imprisonment, will partially reduce the fear and anxiety on women and create an element of pressure on the perpetrator of violence.

The staff to be assigned to the women's desks established in law enforcement units should be formed by trained female personnel, the presence of expert personnel to be assigned by the Provincial Directorate of Family, Social and Policies during the statement stages of women victims of violence, and the presence of lawyers specialized in violence against women during all these procedures may be an indication that women are cared for and valued.

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Ethics Approval

In the writing process of the study titled “Violence against women: Definition, types and the role of men”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the author of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data “Journal of Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the author and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Institutional review board (IRB) approval

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval of this research is not required.